

SYNTHESIS OF TITANIUM ALUMINIDES BASED INTERMETALLIC MATRIX COMPOSITES BY MECHANICAL ALLOYING AND THEIR CONSOLIDATION BY HOT PRESSING

D.D.Mishra^{1,*}, V.Agarwala¹, R.C.Agarwala¹

¹ Department of metallurgical and materials engineering, IIT Roorkee Roorkee, INDIA

* Corresponding author (debbsdmt@iitr.ernet.in)

Keywords: *Mechanical alloying, Titanium Aluminides, Hot pressing, Consolidation*

Abstract

TiAl intermetallics matrix composites have been produced using mechanical alloying technique. A composition of Ti-Al-2Nb-2Cr at% powders was mechanically alloyed for various durations of 20,40,60,80 and 100 hours. At the early stages of milling, a Ti-Al solid solution is formed, which is transformed into an amorphous phase at longer milling times. Traces of TiAl and Ti₃Al were formed with major Ti and Al phases after milling at 40h. When further milled phases of intermetallic compounds like TiAl, Ti₃Al and TiAl₃ started forming after 80 hours of milling and also found in 100 hours milled powders. The powders milled for different durations were hot pressed in Gleeble 3800 at 785⁰C in vacuum. The mechanically alloyed powders as well as the hot pressed compacts were characterized by XRD, FESEM and DTA to determine the phases, crystallite size, hardness, microstructures and the influence of mechanical alloying over hot pressing.

1. Introduction

Ti-Al based intermetallics are recognized as the materials having desirably low density, high strength to weight ratio, high stiffness and good high temperature oxidation resistance. Mechanical alloying is one of the advantageous processes which give rise to a good combination of strength, ductility and nanostructure intermetallics with respect to other powder metallurgical processes [1-7]. MA is specifically a non equilibrium process to produce supersaturated solid solutions, metastable alloys, amorphous phase, micro structural refinement and also for the high structural homogeneity [8,9]. Fabrication of TiAl intermetallic compound by MA and subsequent annealing has been previously reported [10-13] which showed that increasing the milling time resulted in lowering of the crystallite sizes of Ti and Al results in a formation of Ti (Al) solid solution. On continuous milling forming of an amorphous phase occurs. After annealing, the amorphous phase crystallized to a mixture of TiAl and Ti₃Al phases which was already found in

Suryanarayana et al. [8]. Only Ti (Al) solid solution was the only product of milling. By Fadeeva et al. [9] and Bhattacharya et al. [14] reported the appearance of metastable fcc phase during annealing of Ti (Al) solid solution. In the hot pressing process where reactive hot pressing occurs, actually chemical reactions occur for the production of new materials. But where the non-reactive hot pressing occurs, there occur no chemical reactions. The aim of this study is to evaluate the formation of intermetallic compounds during MA and hot pressing processes..

2. Experimental procedure

2.1 Mechanical alloying

Ti (40-44 μ , 99.9% purity), Al (40-44 μ , 99.9% purity), Nb and Cr(40-44 μ ,99.9% purity) powders were mixed to give the composition Ti-48-Al-2Nb-2Cr (at. %) which was then charged into a hardened steel vial with hardened steel balls under a wet toluene media i.e. the balls and charge are totally submerged in the toluene. The charge to ball weight ratio (CBR) was 1:5. The milling was performed in a (Retsch PM 400/2)

ball mill for periods varying from 0 to 100 h at a milling speed of 300 rpm and vial rotation speed of 600 rpm.

Table 1: Milling parameters

2.2 Hot pressing

Hot pressing was performed on two different series of powders: (1) 100 h-milled. (Pre-alloyed) powders for the non-reactive hot pressing process and (2) blended elemental powders for the reactive hot pressing process. The hot pressing was carried at a vacuum of the order of 10^{-4} in Gleeble 3800TM. After hot pressing, the samples were ground and polished.

2.3 Characterization

The milled and hot pressed samples were characterized by means of X-ray diffraction (XRD) using a D8 BRUKER AXS diffractometer with Cu K α , operating at 40 kV and 30 mA. The crystallite size of the as-milled powders was determined by X-ray line broadening and calculated using the Scherrer equation [17]:

$$d = 0.9\lambda/\beta \cos\theta \quad (1)$$

Where $\beta = (\beta_M^2 - \beta_I^2)^{1/2}$, β_M is the full width at half maximum (FWHM), β_I is the correction factor for instrument broadening, θ is the angle of the peak maximum, and λ is the Cu K α weighted wavelength (= 0.15406 nm).

The thermal analysis of the alloyed powders of different milling times and as received powders were carried out up to 1400^oC in a PERKIN ELMER Pyris Diamond TG/DTA. QUANTA FEI-200 Field emission scanning electron microscopy (FESEM) was used to characterize the morphology of the milled powder and the surface morphology of the hot pressed samples. Energy-dispersive analysis of X-Rays (EDAX) coupled with FESEM was used for the semi-quantitative investigation of the microstructure of the hot pressed samples. The density of the hot pressed samples was determined using the immersion method in distilled water based on Archimedes principle.

3. Results and discussion

3.1 MA process

3.1.1 XRD analysis

The evolution of the transformations occurring during milling was followed by XRD. Fig. 1 shows the diffraction pattern for Ti-48Al-2Nb-2Cr. The XRD pattern of as-received powder is almost similar to that 40 h-milled powders. The peak broadening and lowering in the intensity were observed with increase in extent of milling, as the due to the decrease in crystallite size occurring from 90.7-176.8nm after 20 h to about 12-18 nm after 100hours of milling. Shifting of the main reflexion of Ti peaks occurring towards higher angles, that was due to the decrease in the lattice parameter attributed to the distortion of the Ti lattice by Al diffusion. Further milling caused in lowering of the integrated intensity of peaks to decrease which result in the complete amorphization of powders. The amorphization occurs because of the free energy of intermetallics became higher than that of amorphous phase [19].

Fig. 1

According to Fig. 1, after 40 h of MA, the peaks are broadened between angles of 34–42^o; which indicates the amorphization of powders. Interestingly the free energy curve of the amorphous phase in the Ti–Al system is actually lower than those of the solid solution and intermetallic phases which helps in formation of amorphous phases earlier [14]. The diffraction pattern after 80h MA shows the formation of the TiAl intermetallic compound, which is complete after 100 h of MA. TiAl and Ti₃Al intermetallic compounds are the peaks exhibited after 100h MA. According to the results obtained in this section, it may be concluded that the formation of intermetallic compounds is possible during MA. The enthalpy values for the formation of TiAl and Ti₃Al are –75 and –73 kJ/mol respectively and which is the main cause of formation of intermetallics and further heat treatment is required for formation of intermetallics after MA [19].

3.1.2 DTA Study

The thermal analysis datas of the as received Ti-48Al-2Nb-2Cr shown in Fig.2(a), where at 664⁰C the Al got melted and at 785⁰C there is an exothermic peak ,which is the evidence for the formation of TiAl intermetallics. Where the energy released is 39.2 J/g and the exothermic peak shifted to the left with increasing hours of milling. The exothermic peak turned into an impression after 20 hours of milling and the peak temperature came down to the range 250-450⁰C shown in Fig. 2(b), which gives an indication of reactive and non reactive sintering Fig. 2

3.1.3Microstructure

The morphology of as-received and MA-ed powders at different milling times was investigated by FESEM analysis, as shown in Fig. 3. According to Fig. 3a, Ti powders appear in irregular shapes and in various sizes, but the particles of Al are mainly cylindrical or conical. The agglomeration of powders can be clearly observed in the early stages of MA up to 20h due to the ductility of Al. Work hardening and plastic deformation occurs due to further milling, which results in production of finer particles by fragmenting the agglomerated powders which can be easily seen for the powders MA ed from 20h to 80h as shown in Fig. (3b-3e). Further milling upto 100h, abrupt reduction of particle size occurs to a dimension<160nm which is attributed towards the formation of brittle phases (Fig. 3f). Fig.3.

3.2 Hot pressing process

3.2.1 XRD analysis

According to Fig. 4(a) the peaks of the hot pressed samples at 785⁰ C for 5,10 and15 mins of the as received powders showing the formation of TiAl, Ti₃Al TiAl₃, TiAl₂ phases with the formation of AlNb₂ with some retained Ti and Al powder peaks. But Fig. 4(b) and Fig. 4(c) shows the formation of TiAl, Ti₃Al and TiAl₃ for the 80h and 100h MAed powders and

hot pressed for 5,10 and 15mins. The MA ed powders exhibit peaks broadened due to the amorphization occurred by plastic deformation, but the hot pressed samples show sharp peaks, which is due to recrystallization of the phases.

Fig.4.

3.2.2Microstructure

According to the Fig.5a and 5b the micrographs of the 80h and 100h (MAed+HPed for 15 mins) samples at 785⁰C show the phases of Ti, TiAl and Ti₃Al with AlNb₂ where the 100h MA ed powders show finer microstructures. It is obvious from Fig. 5a that the TiAl intermetallic compound has the greatest amounts of the phases though some of the regions showing only the higher percentage Ti. Ti₃Al is only found in some separate islands in the TiAl matrix, with some dispersed AlNb₂.

Fig.5

Physical properties

The density of the sample made with reactive hot pressing (as received) is higher than that of the hot pressed pre-alloyed powder. Both kinds of the hot pressed possess relatively adequate densities to exhibit considerable mechanical properties. Due to the mechanical alloying, lowering of particle sizes and work hardening attribute towards the lowering in the densification. The hardness value of the HP-ed pre-alloyed powder (1175 VHN) is almost three times higher than that of the HP-ed elemental one (403 VHN), which is the effect of mechanical alloying, which cause in the formation of finer intermetallic phases than the HPed elemental powder blends.

Fig.7.

4. Conclusion

The results of this study show that titanium aluminide based intermetallic matrix composites with AlNb₂ phases as reinforcement can be produced by mechanical alloying of elemental Ti and Al at times longer than 80 h followed by hot pressing. Increasing mechanical alloying

time led to a dramatic decrease in the particle size of titanium aluminide powders down to about less than 160 nm and crystallite size in the range 12-18 nm after 100 h of milling. The pre alloyed powders show lower hot pressing temperature (non reactive) and show comparative physical properties with fine grains.

Fig.1: XRD patterns of as-received and milled powders for different times.

Fig. 2. (a) Thermal analysis of as received Ti-48Al-2Nb powder mixture and (b) The starting, peak and the finishing temperature of the

exothermic peak in the thermal analysis datas of powders of different milling times.

Fig.3. FESEM micrographs of as-received and milled powders for different milling times.(a)As-received powder, (b) 10 h MA-ed powder, (c) 20 h MA-ed powder, (d) 40h MA-ed powder, (e) 60 h MA-ed powder, (f) 80 h MA-ed powder and (g) 100 h MA-ed powder.

Fig.4. Comparative XRD patterns of milled ,sintered at 450°C and 800°C for (a) as received (b)20h MA ed (c)80h MA ed and (d)100h MA ed.

Fig.5. FESEM Micrographs of hot pressed samples at 785°C (a) 80h MA ed for 15 mins (b) 100h MA ed for 15 mins.

Fig.7. Comparison of Density of elemental and prealloyed powder samples hot pressed at 785°C for 5 mins, 10 mins and 15 mins.

Planetary Ball mill Details (Retsch PM 400/2)	Milling Parameters
Milling Balls- Hardened steel balls	Milling Media- Toluene
Milling Jars- Hardened steel jars	Charge to Ball ratio- 1:5
Jar capacity- 500 ml	Milling speed- 300 rpm Vial Speed- 600 rpm
PCA-Toluene	Total time of milling- 100h Weight of initial charge- 30gms

References

- [1] C. Suryanarayana, G.E. Korth, F.H. Froes, *Metall. Mater. Trans. A* 28 (1997) 1205–1212.
- [2] A. Takasaki, Y. Furuya, *Nanostruct. Mater.* 11 (1999) 1205–1217.
- [3] L. Lu, M.O. Lai, F.H. Froes, *JOM* 54 (2002) 62–64.
- [4] G.J. Fan, M.X. Quan, Z.Q. Hu, *J. Mater. Sci.* 30 (1995) 4847–4851.
- [5] F. Wenbin, H. Lianxi, H. Wenxiong, W. Erde, L. Xiaoqing, *Mater. Sci. Eng. A* 403 (2005) 186–190.
- [6] F. Zhang, L. Lu, M.O. Lai, F.H. Froes, *J. Mater. Sci.* 38 (2003) 613–619.
- [7] S. Djanarthany, J.-C. Viala, J. Bouix, *Mater. Chem. Phys.* 72 (2001) 301–319.
- [8] C. Suryanarayana, *Mechanical Alloying and Milling*, Marcel Dekker, New York, 2004.
- [9] D.L. Zhang, *Prog. Mater. Sci.* 49 (2004) 537–560.
- [10] C. Suryanarayana, G.E. Korth, F.H. Froes, *Metall. Mater. Trans. A* 28 (1997) 293–302.
- [11] M. Kambara, K. Uenishi, K.F. Kobayashi, *J. Mater. Sci.* 35 (2000) 2897–2905.
- [12] V.I. Fadeeva, A.V. Leonov, E. Szewczak, H. Matyja, *Mater. Sci. Eng. A* 242 (1998) 230–234.
- [13] Y. Liu, W. Liu, *J. Alloys Compd.* 440 (2007) 154–157.
- [14] P. Bhattacharya, P. Bellon, R.S. Averback, S.J. Hales, *J. Alloys Compd.* 368 (2004) 187–196.
- [15] B.D Cullity, *Elements of X-ray Diffraction*, Addison-Welsey, Reading, MA, 1969.
- [16] W. Guo, S. Martelli, N. Burgio, M. Magini, F. Padella, E. Paradiso, I. Soletta, *J. Mater. Sci.* 26 (1990) 6190–6196.
- [17] B.D Cullity, *Elements of X-ray Diffraction*, Addison-Welsey, Reading, MA, 1969.
- [18] J.L. Hay, G.M. Pharr, *ASM Handbook*, vol. 3, ASM International, Materials Park, OH, 2000, p. 54, section 2.
- [19] F.H. Froes, C. Suryanarayana, K. Russell, C.-G. Li, *Mater. Sci. Eng. A* 192/193 (1995) 612–613.